

IMPROVING SECURITY FOR VIRTUAL MACHINES IN CLOUD VIRTUALIZATION

Zareena Taj

Senior Scale Lecturer, Department of CSE, DACG Government Polytechnic,
Chikkamagalore, India

Rangaswamy M G

Senior Scale Lecturer, Department of CSE, Government Polytechnic, Thuruvekere. India

Pavan Kumar H

Senior Scale Lecturer, Department of CSE, Government Polytechnic. Hiriyur, India

ABSTRACT

Cloud computing is a prominent developing technology that primarily focuses on data storage and the provision of on-demand computer resources for diverse applications. Users may save their data on the cloud and access it quickly and effortlessly. The accessibility of cloud data from any location at any time has drawn many users to this technology; yet, a significant concern in this setting is the privacy of user data. The consolidation of many users' data in a single location raises concerns over data privacy among the users. Virtualization is a method used to provide a virtual environment for the identification and isolation of user data. It enables a user to execute numerous operating systems concurrently on a single computer by generating virtual instances of an operating system, server, or network resource. Virtualization enables the operation of numerous servers on a single system while maintaining isolation between them, since they function on distinct virtual machines.

Keywords: Operating System, Servers, Security, Virtualization, Virtual Machine.

Cite this Article: Zareena Taj, Rangaswamy M G, Pavan Kumar H, Improving Security for Virtual Machines in Cloud Virtualization, *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*, 15(5), 2024, pp. 351-365.

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_5/IJCET_15_05_033.pdf

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background

Cloud computing denotes any hosted service provided over the internet. These services often include servers, databases, software, networks, analytics, and many computer operations that may be accessed via the cloud.

Cloud-stored files and applications are accessible to users from any location, negating the need of proximity to physical hardware. Historically, user-generated documents and spreadsheets were required to be stored on a physical hard drive, USB device, or disk. In the absence of a certain hardware component, the data were entirely unavailable outside the computer from which they originated. Cloud computing makes papers accessible universally, since the data resides on a network of hosted computers that send information over the internet.

Fig1. Services of cloud

The user controls the cloud application, while the cloud provider manages the infrastructure. Cloud computing comprises three tiers of services: Software as a Service (SaaS), Platform as a Service (PaaS), and Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS). In SaaS, applications are provided by the cloud provider to the customer via a pay-as-you-go or on-demand approach. Prior to use the services, the user is not required to purchase a license or install the program. This paradigm encompasses systems such as Microsoft Office 365, Google Docs, and Dropbox. In PaaS, the external supplier delivers both the hardware and the software application platforms. PaaS suppliers supply development tools, middleware, operating systems, database management systems, and infrastructure. This approach encompasses platforms such as Heroku, SAP Cloud, and Aneka. In IaaS, public cloud providers provide a comprehensive range of services, including operating systems and servers, on a pay-per-use model. This approach encompasses platforms such as Amazon Web Services (AWS) and Microsoft Azure.

1.2. Working of cloud computing

The cloud is fundamentally a decentralized platform for information sharing over satellite networks. Each cloud application is hosted by a corporation that is accountable for managing the extensive data centers, which provide security, storage capacity, and computational power necessary for handling all user data sent to the cloud.

The foremost firms providing cloud services include big entities such as Amazon (Amazon Web Services) and Google, with several additional providers, both large and small. These hosting firms may sell the rights to use their cloud services and store data on their networks, while also providing the end user with an environment that facilitates communication between devices and applications.

1.3. Virtualization

VMM is the fundamental software that underpins virtualization environments and deployments. Upon installation on a host computer, the Virtual computer Monitor (VMM) enables the creation of virtual machines (VMs), each running with distinct operating systems (OS) and applications. The VMM oversees the backend operations of these VMs by distributing the necessary processing, memory, storage, and other input/output (I/O) resources.

VMM offers a centralized interface for overseeing the operation, status, and availability of virtual machines deployed on a single server or distributed across many networked hosts. Virtualization may be categorized as software virtualization and hardware virtualization, as well as full virtualization and paravirtualization, based on the extent and nature of the virtualization used. Virtualization technology pertains to the implementation of virtualization at the software level. Overall, it may be categorized into two factions: open-source virtualization and commercial virtualization.

Fig 2. Virtualization technology

1.4. Importance of virtualization:

Virtualization is essential for resource maintenance in a cloud computing environment, since it facilitates the process. Virtualization in Cloud Computing enhances security by safeguarding the integrity of both cloud components and guest virtual machines. Cloud Component virtualized computers may be scaled up or down as needed, or they can provide dependability. Managed Service Provider VA offers high usage of pooled resources, resource sharing, and timely provisioning as key elements. The following arguments elucidate the advantages of using a Managed Service Provider VA.

- Streamlined management
- Diminished system administrative tasks
- Facilitated software installation
- Data center consolidation and reduced power consumption
- Enhanced CPU usage
- Virtual machines may operate on any x86 server

1.5. Types of Virtualizations in Cloud Computing

Virtualization has several practical uses. In addition to enabling the execution of an alternative operating system on your device, often referred to as hardware virtualization, it also enables users to dedicate hardware resources to various operations that optimize performance.

1.5.1. Server Virtualization

Physical servers are robust equipment equipped with many processors that store information and programs inside a computer network. To enhance efficiency, each physical server is often allocated to a single application or function. Nonetheless, this may lead to inefficiency since each server utilizes just a portion of its full processing capabilities.

Server virtualization addresses this issue by enabling an administrator to transform a server into many virtual computers. These virtual machines use the server's resources and function as separate physical devices, enabling us to distribute the server's processing power according to our requirements.

Fig 3. Types of virtualizations

1.5.2. Application Virtualization

Traditionally, executing a program utilizes the current operating system and its physical resources. You are executing the program on a PC. Application virtualization isolates the application from the underlying operating system. This provides access to the program without requiring installation on the native device. Program virtualization enables an administrator to install the program on a server. Individuals with access to this server may use the program as if it were installed on their own devices. This offers customers advantages like portability, cross-platform functionality, and the capability to execute numerous instances of the program.

1.5.3. Network Virtualization

A computer network denotes a collection of digitally interconnected computers capable of communicating and sharing resources. Network virtualization denotes the amalgamation of network resources into a unified software-based network. This establishes a virtual network that provides administrative control over all hardware and software resources present on the original network.

Network visualization enables the amalgamation of several networks into a singular entity (external visualization) or the interconnection of software containers into an independent network (internal visualization). Any kind of network visualization enables the segmentation of available bandwidth into distinct channels that may be allocated and reallocated as required.

1.5.4. Desktop Virtualization

Desktop virtualization enables the user to establish a virtual desktop, often hosted in a centralized data center. The user may thereafter access this virtual desktop remotely from any location using a thin client (such as a web browser), thereby establishing a portable workstation.

1.5.5. Storage Virtualization

Storage virtualization denotes the abstraction of numerous physical storage devices into a unified storage cluster, which is administered from a centralized device. These storage devices will then present themselves to the user as a single storage unit.

1.6. Virtualization security technology and protection

Virtualization security technology protects the security of a single virtual machine, including virtualized hardware security technology, virtualized middleware security technology, virtualized software security technology, virtualized data security technology, and virtualized application security technology. When implementing security protection for virtual machines, the firewalls and IDS are installed on virtual machines traditionally, but this will result in a large waste of resources. One of the popular methods is to enable a dedicated virtual machine in the virtualization system to provide security protection services for other service virtual machines by deploying independent security functions such as firewall, intrusion detection, and virus protection on the virtual machine. Another way is to install a firewall in the virtual middleware.

To implement the isolation between virtual machines, the virtual machines can be classified based on service attributes, service security levels, and network attributes. The virtual machine can be isolated by the destination IP, source and destination ports, protocols, resource pools, folders, containers, and so on. It can also be isolated from smaller granularities, such as user identity, service type. It can also be isolated through different IP network segments of the VLAN.

1.6.1. Comparative analysis of safety technology

Table 1. Comparative analysis of safety technology

Kind	Safety Principle	Attack Instance	Attack Effect	Defense Plan
Virtualized hardware security technology	Chip internal module security	Malicious Firmware	Sudden crash	Identity authentication mechanism
Virtualized middleware security technology	Virtual resource pool security	Embedded attack	virtual resource pool Paralysis	Hypervisor protection technology
Virtualized software security technology	Shared memory attack	Stealing service attack	Memory read error	Virtual machine migration
Virtualized data security technology	Ownership and control of data	Security breach attack	Content tampering	Data encryption technology
Virtualized application security technology	Top-level Application security	Denial of service attack	Application not available	Trusted access control technology

By conducting a comparative study of the five suggested virtualized security solutions, an appropriate security protection system may be derived. The security technology of virtualized hardware devices may be safeguarded by the identity authentication process. A security risk presents a significant danger. The security technology of virtualized middleware is mostly maintained by the protective mechanisms of the Hypervisor itself. The security concerns are inferior to those associated with hardware security. Virtualized software security technology may mitigate memory read mistakes via virtual machine migration techniques. Virtualized data security technology may enforce content security via data encryption, while virtualized application security technology can provide top-layer security by using trusted access technology.

1.7. Motivation

The technology and ideas used in Cloud services have yet to realize their full potential, and many capabilities remain underdeveloped and insufficiently investigated for comprehensive utilization. Virtualization plays a crucial role in cloud computing. We cannot anticipate favorable commercial outcomes from the perspective of cloud service providers and satisfactory services from the viewpoint of cloud service users. The cloud yields optimal outcomes just when it is virtualized, standardized, and automated, since users anticipate scalable resources. Competence can only be attained via virtualization, standardization, and automation. This will save costs and enhance service quality. This is undoubtedly an attractive moderate equilibrium, and we see that firms using this get tangible, quantitative trade results. Currently, establishing logical instances at all levels (system, storage, and network) has become crucial for enhancing system security, reliability, and availability, reducing costs, and providing better flexibility. We must document the requirements and explanations for the security of virtualization in a cloud computing environment. Ensuring security in virtualization remains a formidable challenge, regardless of whether the computer environment is basic or sophisticated. In a heterogeneous cloud environment, including public, private, and hybrid clouds, the challenges of cloud computing services are significantly amplified due to their inherent diversity.

1.8. Problem Statement

The technology and ideas used in Cloud services have yet to realize their full potential, and many capabilities remain underdeveloped and insufficiently investigated for comprehensive utilization. Virtualization plays a crucial role in cloud computing. We cannot anticipate favorable commercial outcomes from the perspective of cloud service providers and satisfactory services from the viewpoint of cloud service users. The cloud yields optimal outcomes just when it is virtualized, standardized, and automated, since users anticipate scalable resources. Competence can only be attained via virtualization, standardization, and automation. This will save costs and enhance service quality. This is undoubtedly an attractive moderate equilibrium, and we see that firms using this get tangible, quantitative trade results. Currently, establishing logical instances at all levels (system, storage, and network) has become crucial for enhancing system security, reliability, and availability, reducing costs, and providing better flexibility. We must document the requirements and explanations for the security of virtualization in a cloud computing environment. Ensuring security in virtualization remains a formidable challenge, regardless of whether the computer environment is basic or sophisticated. In a heterogeneous cloud environment, including public, private, and hybrid clouds, the challenges of cloud computing services are significantly amplified due to their inherent diversity.

2. RELATED WORK

In every field of employment, particularly in research, it is essential to possess a comprehensive awareness of prior contributions by other scholars. It is crucial to do a thorough study of prior contributions, enabling us to precisely articulate the issue statement, so allowing the research to pursue more objective-oriented routes. This aids us in identifying actions that should be avoided to save experimental and design time. In our study endeavor, many distinct research publications have been examined, and a concise overview is provided below:

In cloud computing, Jingare, P., et al [1] elucidate that virtualization serves as the foundation for offering Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS), which decouples data, network, applications, and computers from hardware limitations. This article examines several facets of Cloud virtualization security. The author identified: i) security requirements for virtualization in cloud computing, which might serve as a foundation for safeguarding the virtual infrastructure of the cloud, and ii) potential attacks that may target cloud virtual infrastructure. The document has identified many security vulnerabilities inside the virtual machine environment. Certain risks outlined above may be seen as advantages in certain contexts; nonetheless, they are included to emphasize the need of exercising caution throughout the design and implementation of the virtual environment. Virtualization is an effective strategy for minimizing operating expenses in contemporary computing; nevertheless, if improperly implemented, it might pose a hazard to the environment.

Ding, W et al. [2] have presented the evolution of virtualization and examined the architecture and commercial virtualization products. Subsequently, virtualization technology was implemented in the cloud. Computing is developing the cloud platform with VMware vCloud technologies. The effectiveness of server virtualization assessment on the cloud platform is described with instances of the installation procedure. Our research and analysis in virtualization and cloud computing have yielded many performance enhancements. Chen, L et al [3] presents the prevalent virtualization technology, examines the security vulnerabilities associated with virtualization in cloud computing, and proposes related countermeasures. Virtualization significantly reduces administrative expenses while enhancing the availability and flexibility of physical resources.

Virtualization, as the foundation of cloud computing technology, is encountering security issues that impede the fast development and widespread adoption of cloud computing. Analyzing the primary security risks to virtualization technology and enhancing its security measures is of paramount importance.

Virtualization is a fundamental component of cloud computing and enhances its value, as noted by Majumder et al [4]. Cloud computing refers to the provision of shared computing resources, such as software, infrastructure, platforms, or data, as a service and on demand over the internet. Virtualization has regained significance as a means to enhance system security and optimize the exploitation of underlying resources by generating virtual representations of existing physical cloud resources. This study analyzes the security issues associated with virtualization in cloud services and proposes a virtualization security architecture along with potential solutions.

Recently, virtualization and cloud computing have emerged as two prominent study areas, as noted by Rashid, A et al [5]. Unlike in the past, an increasing number of organizations are utilizing virtualization for server consolidation, dynamic load balancing, testing and development, disaster recovery, enhanced system reliability and security, power consumption reduction, high availability for critical applications, and the optimization of application deployment and migrations. Information Technology resources may be provided as services over the Internet to the end user via cloud computing. Virtualization is a fundamental technology of cloud computing. This article provides a comprehensive examination of virtualization. Additionally, we examined the role of virtualization in cloud computing and the three main kinds of virtualization technology.

Cloud computing technology [6] offers a comprehensive internet platform including several on-demand services. Cloud computing delivers services economically over the internet in a dependable and efficient manner. Cloud computing decreases expenditures associated with acquiring gear, software, and software licensing by offering services on a rental basis. It lowers licensing expenses and offers backups to maintain numerous data copies. This article presents a study aimed at identifying research challenges related to virtualization in cloud computing, which offers a comprehensive online platform including several on-demand services.

Virtualization technology [7] has limited security capabilities for safeguarding expansive environments such as the cloud. Consequently, the establishment of a resilient security system necessitates modifications to conventional virtualization design. This research presents a novel security architecture for hypervisor-based virtualization technologies to enhance the security of the cloud environment. This study proposes a virtualization architecture to enhance cloud security. The suggested design aims to alleviate the strain, decentralize security responsibilities between the hypervisor and virtual machines, and transform the centralized security system into a distributed framework. The distributed security system effectively alleviates the strain of hypervisor-based virtualization; yet, this dispersion may introduce vulnerabilities to the cloud. Furthermore, distributed security systems exhibit greater complexity than their centralized counterparts.

Di Pietro et al. [8] elucidate the aims of illuminating contemporary virtualization technology and its progress concerning security, with a focus on its uses inside the Cloud environment. This study asserts that virtualization is fundamental to cloud computing. Although more lightweight methods like Containerization and Unikernels are available, hardware-supported isolation techniques provide advantages in several contexts where security considerations are pertinent. Nonetheless, security vulnerabilities remain a significant concern, as seen by newly identified exploits. Advanced virtualization techniques and improved isolation and monitoring technologies, which may also use the extra computational resources of contemporary CPUs and GPUs, remain in their nascent stages.

These advancements, together with suitable software equivalents, may enhance the integrity and security of resources in cloud environments, server farms, and mobile contexts.

Sun, J et al [9] delineate the advantages of cloud computing for enterprises, including cost savings, expedited implementation, and dynamic scalability, while noting that virtualization technology introduces possible dangers and vulnerabilities to network security. Based on the characteristics of cloud computing technology, we propose strategies and methodologies for enhancing network security. The meticulous management procedures at both the virtual machine level and the security domain level enhance the security of the virtual network environment.

Cloud computing [10] is a contemporary technology that enhances application capabilities regarding functionality, flexible resource management, and collaborative execution methodologies. Virtualization is the core component of cloud computing, facilitating the dynamic on-demand deployment of IT resources in both industrial and academic settings. The resources manifest in several ways, including network, server, storage, application, and client. This study focuses on how virtualization enhances the flexibility of resources in a cloud computing context. This study provides a comprehensive analysis of open-source virtualization approaches, associated problems, and prospective research directions.

Kiran Kumar et al. [11] examined the virtualization underlying cloud computing. It elucidates both cloud computing and virtualization. Virtualization enhances the efficacy of cloud computing. Virtualization utilizes many resources like as input/output, operating systems, networks, and storage. Virtualization enhances scalability while making cloud solutions economically viable. These two technologies complement one other in delivering cutting-edge services to end consumers. Individuals and companies may use many types of cloud services on a pay-per-use basis, including infrastructure, platform, and software solutions. Scientific and high-performance computer operations may use cloud computing.

Tiwari, V et al [12] have elucidated the concept of virtualization in cloud computing, its many sorts, distinct approaches, and the rationale for its significant potential, emphasizing the need of integrating this system into your IT infrastructure. Cloud virtualization facilitates the streamlined establishment of environments on the cloud, hence reducing the need for extensive management. Through this strategy, the cloud user distributes data stored in the cloud, which may include application software, among other items. Establishing a virtual platform for server operating systems and storage devices, while monitoring the availability and use of physical resources for virtual resources, is essential. The virtualization technology primarily facilitates the provision of a pool of IT resources, enabling resource sharing to derive different business advantages. Typically, this is achieved by centralizing administrative functions to enhance scalability, productivity, and workload management, resulting in significant advantages for several enterprises. Consequently, virtualization is increasingly becoming popular.

Oludele et al. [13] elucidate that cloud computing is a technology enabling the provision of computing resources to clients/subscribers over extensive distances. Additionally, they discuss virtualization, a component technology that allows multiple guest systems to coexist on a single host machine, sharing its computing resources. Both technologies have gained significant popularity and experienced substantial advancements in the 21st century. This review paper offers a comprehensive overview of virtualization and cloud computing technologies, including their historical development and progress, and indicating potential future improvements in these fields.

Srivastava, P et al [14] examined the architecture and prominent platforms of cloud computing technologies. It also examined the problems and concerns associated with cloud technology. Despite several limits and the need for improved methodological procedures, cloud computing is growing as a very appealing paradigm, particularly for big companies.

Cloud computing projects may impact organizations within two to three years, since they possess the ability to fundamentally transform the IT sector.

Gowda, T et al [15] provide a comprehensive assessment of virtualization technology and its significance in cloud computing. This study succinctly elucidates cloud computing and the emergence of virtualization within it. We have examined the evaluation of virtualization in cloud computing, its evolution within the IT business, and highlighted many significant functions of virtualization, along with its advantages and disadvantages in the contemporary landscape. Virtualization encompasses numerous varieties, enhancing its significance in the contemporary IT landscape. As virtualization is increasingly accepted in the current sector, research continues to advance the frontiers of virtualization for the future.

The increasing need for advanced technology [16] and efficient environments has led to the emergence of cloud computing, characterized by its highly dispersed nature and the provision of on-demand services. The inherent openness and service delivery in a virtualized manner render cloud computing environments susceptible to many types of assaults. This study presents a taxonomy detailing different security vulnerabilities in cloud settings, particularly at the virtualization layer. In addition to a concise examination of potential threats to the cloud virtualization layer and the current mitigation strategies, we have sought to identify areas necessitating further attention to enhance cloud virtualization security.

M. Almutairy et al. [17] assert that virtualization has emerged as a prevalent and appealing technique in cloud computing settings. The allocation of a single physical machine across numerous isolated virtual machines enhances hardware utilization and facilitates more efficient migration and maintenance of virtual systems compared to their physical equivalents. Virtualization is an essential technology inside a cloud ecosystem. The existence of an extra abstraction layer between software and hardware introduces new security vulnerabilities.

Security concerns associated with virtualization technology have emerged as a substantial problem for enterprises owing to the introduction of new security risks. This study seeks to delineate the primary issues and hazards associated with virtualization in cloud computing systems. Additionally, it addresses prevalent virtual risks and assaults that compromise the security of cloud computing. The study aimed to gather the perspectives of cloud stakeholders about virtualization vulnerabilities, threats, and potential mitigation strategies. We present ideas for enhancing security and lowering risks associated with virtualization, which are essential for adopting safe cloud computing.

Kumar, N et al. [18] examined security issues in cloud virtualization. We then offer several strategies to mitigate the vulnerabilities of virtual machines and virtual machine monitors. Although a virtualized IT infrastructure encounters similar security difficulties as physical server settings, we may use our investment in multiprocessor, multi-core architectures and virtualization software to provide the necessary security methods for their protection. Utilizing a combined approach with security software facilitates enhanced protection, prompt solution implementation, and establishes a fundamental security standard for all virtual machines, while avoiding bottlenecks or superfluous restrictions.

This research [19] elucidated the primary aspects of VM Escape assaults. Commencing with the concept of VM Escape and concluding with the strategies used to mitigate or suppress it. Moreover, we have halted the use of many tools and procedures that may initiate a VM Escape assault. Despite the restrictions available to address VM Escape assaults, whether alone or in conjunction with other potential threats, VM Escape remains a persistent challenge for cloud environments.

Virtualization [20] has emerged as a critical domain in recent years, driven by the expansion of data centers and cloud computing. The predominant forms of virtualization architecture are native virtualization and hosted virtualization; in native virtualization, the hypervisor operates directly on the hardware, while in hosted virtualization, the hypervisor functions atop a hosted operating system. The deployment of virtualization in a data center or cloud introduces four new essential features that alter the use of security mechanisms.

The survey of reviewed research papers indicates that the majority of researchers primarily focus on the security of the Hypervisor or Virtual Machine Monitor (VMM), as the Hypervisor is instrumental in generating virtual resources according to situational demands. The researchers believe that the primary security danger is inside the Hypervisor, necessitating a focus on the security of the Virtual Machine Monitor. Numerous researchers have proposed various frameworks aimed at securing the Virtual Machine Monitor, addressing specific scenarios within the IT sector. Some solutions cater to particular cloud service models, such as Infrastructure-as-a-Service (IaaS) or Platform-as-a-Service (PaaS), while others are tailored to distinct deployment models, including public or private clouds. The majority of the offered solutions pertain to the unique models of individual vendor products, such as Xen and VMware.

Our system's primary objective is to discover and eliminate such issues. Additionally, halting the virtual machines affected by the aforementioned issues prevents the disruption or corruption of other operational virtual machines. The primary benefit of this solution is its applicability across any cloud service or deployment type. It is applicable in any scenario where there are potential hazards to the virtual environment, particularly with virtual machines. It also encompasses multilayer security methods to detect and rectify the virtualized settings.

3. VIRTUALIZATION IN CLOUD COMPUTING

Virtualization often generates several virtual resources from a single physical resource.

- The Host Machine is the physical machine on which a virtual computer is created.
- Guest Machine - The virtual machines instantiated on a Host Machine are referred to as Guest Machines.

3.1. Why Virtualization in Cloud Computing?

Virtualization is a crucial idea in cloud computing. In cloud computing, a cloud provider has all physical resources, such as servers, storage devices, and network equipment, which are leased to users, alleviating their concerns over these physical assets.

Fig 4. Virtualization in Cloud Computing

Providing physical services on a rental basis per client is prohibitively expensive, since it incurs significant costs and users are unlikely to use the services in their whole. This issue may be addressed with virtualization. This strategy is not only effective in using physical services but also reduces vendor expenses. Consequently, cloud vendors may optimize their large servers and provide lower-spec servers to several clients.

3.2. Pros of Virtualization in Cloud Computing

Virtualization in cloud computing has several advantages, contributing to its widespread adoption among major cloud infrastructure providers.

1. Protection from Failure

A significant advantage of using virtualization in cloud computing is its capacity to avert total system failure. The virtualized infrastructure is compartmentalized into containers, ensuring that a failure in one component does not precipitate a failure in the others. Testing various applications or a new program inside a virtual machine helps safeguard the broader IT environment from problems, viruses, bugs, or application failures.

2. Easy to Transfer Machines or Data

A significant advantage of virtualization is the seamless transmission of data between devices and servers, eliminating the need to hunt through many physical hard drives or data centers for required information. Virtualized desktops and storage enable the seamless movement of whole computers across locations without the need of relocating any physical infrastructure. This conserves organizational time, resources, and finances.

3. Security

Downloading a dangerous file or allowing an attacker to install malware or a virus on our computers often results in virtual machines and infrastructure being effectively isolated from other system components, so significantly impeding the proliferation of viruses and malware across the environment.

Utilizing cloud computing services with virtualization enhances security, since robust encryption methods safeguard data against attackers. In virtualized systems, backups and replicas of data and computers may be effortlessly generated, allowing for seamless restoration in the event of infrastructure breach.

4. Streamlined Processing and Operations

Moreover, the aggregation and virtualization of resources facilitate the implementation of centralized management procedures, hence enhancing the operational efficiency of both business and IT functions. Virtual networks and cloud computing facilitate management by eliminating the need to coordinate individual devices and resources. Also, may concentrate on comprehensive resource management and capacity planning on a broader scale.

This liberates IT personnel and resources to concentrate on alternative tasks, since they need less time managing physical infrastructure concerning repairs, installs, patching, software, and upkeep. In the event of issues, backups and recoveries are expedited, resulting in reduced troubleshooting duration.

5. Cost

Ultimately, a significant advantage of using virtualization in cloud computing or any IT environment is its cost-effectiveness. By partitioning real resources to accommodate numerous virtual desktops and servers, we need less storage capacity and diminished physical infrastructure. This leads to reduced initial expenses and diminished recurring expenditures related to power or leasing payments for the premises.

3.2. Cons of Virtualization

1. Data can be at Risk

Working on virtual instances on shared resources means that our data is hosted on third party resource which put's our data in vulnerable condition. Any hacker can attack on our data or try to perform unauthorized access. Without Security solution our data is in threaten situation.

2. Learning New Infrastructure

As Organization shifted from Servers to Cloud. They required skilled staff who can work with cloud easily. Either they hire new IT staff with relevant skill or provide training on that skill which increase the cost of company.

3. High Initial Investment

It is true that Virtualization will reduce the cost of companies but also it is truth that Cloud has high initial investment. It provides numerous services which are not required and when unskilled organization will try to set up in cloud, they purchase unnecessary services which are not even required to them.

4. CONCLUSION

Virtualization is a cost-effective and energy-efficient strategy used by cloud providers to optimize system utilization and enhance security. Nevertheless, it has additional weaknesses and necessitates the reorganization of manual security protocols. Ensuring the maintenance and security of all virtual machines (VMs) is a problem owing to the fast generation of instances and settings. The data of each guest operating system is preserved as virtual disks, which may be jeopardized if viewed, duplicated, or altered by unauthorized individuals. The hypervisor offers an extra layer of abstraction from real hardware, mitigating malicious assaults and facilitating external monitoring. The hypervisor must rigorously regulate communication between virtual machines and restrict resource use to a defined limit to avoid denial-of-service attacks.

Technology is advancing swiftly, and cloud computing has the potential to expedite future progress. Virtual services have a potential future within IT sectors due to evolving consumer mindsets and increasing company expectations. As flexibility, agility, and portability within IT infrastructures continue to rise, virtualization will assume a central role in the future.

The security of virtual cloud computing is becoming more complex owing to the enhanced security measures of virtual machines and servers relative to physical technology. Compliance approaches may enhance the security of the virtual environment against emerging risks. Minimizing migration time and data loss, together with attributes such as decreased energy consumption, enhanced hardware efficiency, and heightened sustainability, will facilitate the transformation of enterprises within the virtualization software sector.

REFERENCES

- [1] Jingare, P., & Sorte, P. P. (2021). Security Aspects of Virtualization in Cloud Computing. 12(3), 169–172.
- [2] Ding, W., Ghansah, B., & Wu, Y. (2016). Research on the Virtualization technology in Cloud computing environment. *International Journal of Engineering Research in Africa*, 21(6), 191–196. <https://doi.org/10.4028/www.scientific.net/JERA.21.191>
- [3] Chen, L., Xian, M., Liu, J., & Wang, H. (2020). Research on Virtualization Security in Cloud Computing. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*, 806(1). <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/806/1/012027>
- [4] Majumder, A., Roy, S., & Biswas, S. (2015). Data security issues and solutions in cloud computing. *Web-Based Services: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications*, 3(14), 2076–2095. <https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-9466-8.ch091>
- [5] Rashid, A., & Chaturvedi, A. (2019). Virtualization and its Role in Cloud Computing Environment. *International Journal of Computer Sciences and Engineering*, 7(4), 1131–1136. <https://doi.org/10.26438/ijcse/v7i4.11311136>
- [6] Kumar, A. (2020). Research Issues in Virtualization in Cloud Computing. *International Journal of New Innovations in Engineering and Technology Research*, 12(4), 150–159.
- [7] Sabahi, F. (2012). Secure Virtualization for Cloud Environment Using Hypervisor-based Technology. *International Journal of Machine Learning and Computing*, 2(1), 39–45. <https://doi.org/10.7763/ijmlc.2012.v2.87>
- [8] Di Pietro, R., & Lombardi, F. (2018). Virtualization technologies and cloud security: Advantages, issues, and perspectives. *Lecture Notes in Computer Science (Including Subseries Lecture Notes in Artificial Intelligence and Lecture Notes in Bioinformatics)*, 11170 LNCS, 166–185. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-04834-1_9
- [9] Sun, J., Zeng, Y., Shi, G., Li, W., & Li, Z. (2018). The Research for Virtualization Network Security on Cloud Computing. 146(Icaita), 145–148. <https://doi.org/10.2991/icaita-18.2018.37>
- [10] Usha, M. (2014). A Study on Forensic Challenges in Cloud Computing Environments. *Journal of NanoScience and NanoTechnology*, 2(3), 291–295. [http://indiasciencetech.com/index.php?journal=nanotechnology&page=article&op=view&path\[\]=82](http://indiasciencetech.com/index.php?journal=nanotechnology&page=article&op=view&path[]=82)
- [11] Kiran Kumar, D., Sarachandrica, T. P., Rajasekhar, B., Jayasankar, P., & Professor, A. (2014). Review on Virtualization for Cloud Computing. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer and Communication Engineering*, 3(8), 2278–1021. www.ijarce.com
- [12] Tiwari, V., Garg, B., & Pradesh, M. (2020). Study on Virtualization Technology and Its Importance in Cloud. 8(2), 966–972.
- [13] Oludele, A., C. Ogu, E., ‘Shade, K., & Chinecherem, U. (2014). On the Evolution of Virtualization and Cloud Computing: A Review. *Journal of Computer Sciences and Applications*, 2(3), 40–43. <https://doi.org/10.12691/jcsa-2-3-1>
- [14] Srivastava, P., & Khan, R. (2018). A Review Paper on Cloud Computing. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Computer Science and Software Engineering*, 8(6), 17. <https://doi.org/10.23956/ijarcsse.v8i6.711>
- [15] Gowda, T., Vanishree, S., Varshitha, M. S., Yashaswini, K., & Nethravathi, B. (2021). OVERVIEW OF VIRTUALIZATION IN CLOUD COMPUTING. 07, 1841–1846.
- [16] Buch, D. (2018). Taxonomy on Cloud Computing Security Issues at Virtualization Layer. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Engineering and Technology (IJARET)*, 9(4), 50–76. <http://www.iaeme.com/IJARET/index.asp50http://www.iaeme.com/IJARET/issues.asp?JType=IJARET&VType=9&IType=4http://www.iaeme.com/IJARET/issues.asp?JType=IJARET&VType=9&IType=4>

- [17] M. Almutairy, N., & H. A. Al-Shqeerat, K. (2019). A Survey on Security Challenges of Virtualization Technology in Cloud Computing. *International Journal of Computer Science and Information Technology*, 11(03), 95–105. <https://doi.org/10.5121/ijcsit.2019.11308>
- [18] Kumar, N. L. U., & Siddappa, M. (2016). Meeting the challenge of Virtualization impact on Cloud services. 7(1), 457–461.
- [19] Abusaimah, H. (2020). Virtual machine escape in cloud computing services. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications*, 11(7), 327–331. <https://doi.org/10.14569/IJACSA.2020.0110743>.
- [20] Jain, R. (n.d.). Virtualization Security in Data Centers and Clouds. 1–12.

Citation: Zareena Taj, Rangaswamy M G, Pavan Kumar H, Improving Security for Virtual Machines in Cloud Virtualization, *International Journal of Computer Engineering and Technology (IJCET)*, 15(5), 2024, pp. 351-365

Abstract Link: https://iaeme.com/Home/article_id/IJCET_15_05_033

Article Link:

https://iaeme.com/MasterAdmin/Journal_uploads/IJCET/VOLUME_15_ISSUE_5/IJCET_15_05_033.pdf

Copyright: © 2024 Authors. This is an open-access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

This work is licensed under a **Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0)**.

✉ editor@iaeme.com